

VECTOR QUANTIZATION OF A PARAMETRIC SOURCE

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ABSTRACT: *Interpreting the problem in terms of statistical risk, an approach is suggested in this paper for quantizing a parametric source with unknown statistics. Unlike universal quantizers, the suggested method achieves its optimal performance on a fixed dimension basis, and can be used to find a quantizer which minimizes the maximum quantization error when a source belongs to a class of parameterized sources.*

I. INTRODUCTION

A method and two algorithms are suggested for finding a quantizer which minimizes the "worst-case" quantization error. The algorithms are based on an approach for calculating the rate distortion function for a class of parameterized sources (Wolfe, IEEE Transactions on Information Theory, vol. 41, 1995) and another for solving minimax problems (Nelson, Annals of Math. Stats., vol. 37, 1966). Topological theorems are also derived about the two quantizers performance.

Previous approaches include a 1994 method by Effros, Chou, and Gray [1] that employed a weighted universal vector technique and variable dimension vector quantization strategy. Also suggested were Ziv's [10] universal coding and Neuhoff's robust coding techniques [7]. Although it also carves a space into subspaces, the method in this paper utilizes a minimax approach in contrast to Effros *et al's* approach, and unlike Ziv or Neuhoff's method uses relative entropy to measure the distortion.

A shortcoming of any minimax approach is that finding one quantizer which minimizes the "worst-case" quantization error may, in general, yield more average distortion than a universal quantizer which has been designed to perform nearly optimally for all sources in the class. However, an important advantage of the method suggested in this paper is that it achieves optimal performance on a fixed dimension basis, unlike universal quantizers which generally require increasing dimensionality to achieve their full theoretical performance capability. Thus, the method's optimal level of performance is both achievable and predictable on that fixed dimension basis.

Preliminaries are reviewed in Section II. In Section III an approach and two algorithms are presented to find a N -level quantizer which minimizes the "worst-case" quantization error for a source with an unknown parameter. Section IV gives a numerical example, and conclusions are drawn in Section V.

II. PRELIMINARIES

Define q^N as a real-valued mapping from a M -dimensional continuous space $X^M \equiv \times_{i=1}^M X_i$ onto a discrete space Y^N of size N . Then, q^N is a vector quantizer defined by a reproduction space Y^N and a partition $\{S_i\}_{i=1}^N$ such that $S_i = \{\underline{x}^M \in X^M: q^N(\underline{x}^M) = y_i^N, y_i^N \in Y^N\}$ where $\underline{x}^M = (x_1, \dots, x_M)$ has continuous valued x_i and the y_i take values in a discrete set Y^N . Apparently, $Y^N = \{y_i^N\}_{i=1}^N \subset \{Y^N\}$ which is the generally uncountable set of all possible Y^N . Clearly, $\cup_{i=1}^N S_i = X^M$ where $S_i \cap S_j = \emptyset$ for all i, j . If $M=1$, q^N is a N -level scalar quantizer where N is usually finite. When $M \geq 2$, q^N is a vector quantizer.

Let X^M have probability density function p^θ with

parameter $\theta \in \Lambda$ and, furthermore, define $\rho(\underline{x}^M, y^N)$ as a non-negative measure of the distortion caused by the reproduction of \underline{x}^M by y^N . When a partition $\{S_i\}_{i=1}^N$ and reproduction space Y^N are given, the average distortion or mean quantization error of the corresponding quantizer q^N with respect to the joint distribution f^θ is completely specified by the following equation:

$$\begin{aligned} E(\rho(X^M, Y^N)) &= \int_{y^N \in Y^N} dy^N \int_{\underline{x}^M \in X^M} d\underline{x}^M \cdot f^\theta(\underline{x}^M, y^N) \cdot \rho(\underline{x}^M, y^N) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^N \int_{\underline{x}^M \in S_i} d\underline{x}^M \cdot p^\theta(\underline{x}^M) \cdot \rho(\underline{x}^M, y_i^N) \\ &\equiv \rho(q^N, p^\theta) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where the average distortion depends implicitly on parameter θ .

A N -level quantizer q^* achieves a minimum level of quantization error, according to a nearest neighbor criterion, by constructing a partition $\{S_i^*\}_{i=1}^N$ and reproduction space Y^* , where $S_i^* = \{\underline{x}^M \in X^M: q^N(\underline{x}^M) = y_i^*; y_i^* \in Y^*\}$ such that:

$$\rho(\underline{x}^M, y_i^*) = \inf_{y_i^* \in \{Y^*\}} \rho(\underline{x}^M, y_i^N); \underline{x}^M \in S_i^* \quad (2)$$

By construction q^* is optimal over the set of all possible quantizers $\Psi \equiv \{q^N(\{S_i\}_{i=1}^N, Y^N)\}$ for the nearest neighbor design rules stated in equation (2); that is:

$$\rho(q^*, p^\theta) = \inf_{q^N \in \Psi} \rho(q^N, p^\theta), \quad (3)$$

with respect to (2), and where $Y^* = \{y_i^*\}_{i=1}^N \subset \{Y^N\}$ which is the generally uncountable set of all possible reproduction spaces.

Although non-optimal quantizers have no such dependence, it is clear that an optimal quantizer q^* depends implicitly on θ . Rather than writing $q^*(\theta)$, $\{S_i^*(\theta)\}_{i=1}^N$ and $y_i^*(\theta)$, these will usually be abbreviated by q^* , $\{S_i^*\}_{i=1}^N$ and y_i^* respectively, except when emphasizing the implicit dependence of an optimal quantizer or reproduction space on $\theta \in \Lambda$.

Observe that the infimum in equation (2) can be replaced by the minimum when, for each \underline{x}^M , the distortion measure ρ is assumed to be a convex and lower semicontinuous function defined on a compact set. This is because of a result in [2, Lemma 1, p. 84] which shows that the infimum and minimum exist when the decision space is lower semicontinuous.

For each known θ , $\rho(q^N, p^\theta)$ is lower semicontinuous in q^N when $\rho(\underline{x}^M, y^N)$ is lower semicontinuous in y^N because of the convexity assumption. That is, $\rho(q^N, p^\theta)$ is a convex combination of lower semicontinuous functions and each achieves its infimum according to Lemma 1 in [2, p. 84]. Thus, the infimum over all such quantizers can be achieved which implies that there exists an optimal $q^* \in \Psi$ with respect to $\rho(q^N, p^\theta)$.

Given a known input distribution p^θ , methods such as those suggested in [4,5] are available to find an optimal quantizer for certain classes of distortion measures $\rho(\underline{x}^M, y^N)$. Unfortunately, in practice the source statistics are seldom known and the distribution must first be approximated before such a method can

be used to design a N -level quantizer. However, when it is known that the unknown source belongs to a class of parameterized sources an approach presented in the next Section may be used to approximate an optimal quantizer within any pre-determined error threshold when the design criterion is one to minimize the "worst case" quantization error.

III. QUANTIZER DESIGN

The method utilizes relative entropy (*i.e.* discrimination, cross entropy) as a measure of the similarity between sources in order to group together within a finite number of subclasses, all sources in a class whose entropies are within a previously specified level of discrepancy. A set of representative sources can then be selected to find a N -level quantizer which minimizes the maximum quantization error with respect to a given non-negative distortion measure and a given threshold of error.

Begin by considering a source which is known only to belong to a class of stationary parameterized sources. That is, consider an unknown stationary source X^M with probability density function p^θ and unknown parameter $\theta \in \Lambda$ where Λ is compact. Let $\rho(x^M, y_i^N)$ be the non-negative distortion measure for reproduction of $x^M \in X^M$ by $y^N \in Y^N$. Assume that the distortion measure ρ is convex and lower semicontinuous in y^N . The design criteria that we shall continue to use is one to minimize the maximum mean quantization error for a class of parameterized sources given by $\theta \in \Lambda$ (see equations 2 and 3).

Recall that an optimal quantizer and, therefore, the corresponding partition and reproduction space depend implicitly on θ . Thus, the quantizer which minimizes the maximum mean quantization error may be found by examining the entire class of all quantizers Ψ over each member of the class of sources given by parameter space Λ . Such a N -level quantizer q^* with an optimum partition $\{S_i^*\}_{i=1}^N$ and reproduction space Y^* satisfies (4).

$$\begin{aligned} \sup_{\theta \in \Lambda} \rho(q^*, p^\theta) &= \sup_{\theta \in \Lambda} E(\rho(X^M, Y^*)) \\ &= \sup_{\theta \in \Lambda} \left(\sum_{i=1}^N \left(\min_{y_i^N \in \{y^N\}} \int_{x^M \in S_i} dx^M p^\theta(x^M) \cdot \rho(x^M, y_i^N) \right) \right) \quad (4) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\min_{y_i^N \in \{y^N\}} \left(\sup_{\theta \in \Lambda} \int_{x^M \in S_i} dx^M p^\theta(x^M) \cdot \rho(x^M, y_i^N) \right) \right). \end{aligned}$$

Given the previous assumptions the supremum and minimum can be interchanged in the second and third equalities because of a result in [2] which is explained in the following. First, observe that the supremum of a family of lower semicontinuous functions is also lower semicontinuous according to Lemma 2 in [2, p. 84]. Additionally, theorem 2 in [2, p. 85] states that a minimax problem has a value, and thus, a solution can be achieved when Λ is compact and ρ is lower semicontinuous in y^N for all θ . Clearly, equation (4) is a minimax problem. The remaining conditions are also assumed in equation (4) from the preceding discussion, and therefore, the supremum and minimum can be interchanged.

Thus, equation (4) states the existence of an optimal N -level quantizer q^* which minimizes the maximum mean quantization error over the class of all sources given by Λ , in the sense of equations (2) and (3). From (4) it clearly follows that:

$$\sup_{\theta \in \Lambda} \rho(q^*, p^\theta) = \min_{q^N \in \Psi} \sup_{\theta \in \Lambda} \rho(q^N, p^\theta). \quad (5)$$

Now, consider a related Bayes problem. Let $\tau \in \Xi$ be a given distribution and define:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{P}(\tau, q^N) &\equiv \int_{\theta \in \Lambda} d\theta \cdot \tau(\theta) \cdot \left(\int_{y^M \in Y^N} dy^N \int_{x^M \in X^M} dx^M \cdot f^\theta(x^M, y^N) \cdot \rho(x^M, y^N) \right) \\ &= \int_{\theta \in \Lambda} d\theta \cdot \tau(\theta) \cdot \left(\sum_{i=1}^N \int_{x^M \in S_i^M} dx^M \cdot p^\theta(x^M) \cdot \rho(x^M, y_i^N) \right) \\ &= \int_{\theta \in \Lambda} d\theta \cdot \tau(\theta) \cdot \rho(q^N, p^\theta). \quad (6) \end{aligned}$$

Taking the minimum of both sides of (6), for a given τ , yields a quantizer q^* defined by:

$$\mathcal{P}(\tau, q^*) = \min_{q^N \in \Psi} \int_{\theta \in \Lambda} d\theta \cdot \tau(\theta) \cdot \rho(q^N, p^\theta), \quad (7)$$

where $y_i^* \in \{y^N\}$ is determined by:

$$y_i^* = \arg(\rho(x^M, y_i^*)) = \arg \left(\min_{y_i^N \in \{y^N\}} \rho(x^M, y_i^N) \right). \quad (8)$$

Thus, q^* is Bayes with respect to the given *a priori* distribution τ . The Bayes risk corresponds to the mean quantization error and q^* minimizes both the *a priori* and *a posteriori* risks. Taking the supremum over both sides of equation (7) with respect to Ξ yields the following equation:

$$\mathcal{P}(\tau^*, q^*) = \sup_{\tau \in \Xi} \min_{q^N \in \Psi} \mathcal{P}(\tau, q^N). \quad (9)$$

However, the *a priori* distribution is not known in this problem, and in accordance with the design criteria, the objective is to find a quantizer q^* and least favorable distribution τ^* which minimize the maximum quantization error over a class of sources.

Theorem 1: Let there be given a non-negative distortion measure ρ which is convex and lower semicontinuous in y^N . Also, let there be given a class of sources with parameter space Λ that is compact with respect to ρ , and a distribution p^θ . Then, there is a quantizer q^* such that:

$$\begin{aligned} \sup_{\theta \in \Lambda} \rho(q^*, p^\theta) &= \min_{q^N \in \Psi} \sup_{\theta \in \Lambda} \rho(q^N, p^\theta) \\ &= \sup_{\tau \in \Xi} \min_{q^N \in \Psi} \mathcal{P}(\tau, q^N) \quad (10) \\ &= \sup_{\tau \in \Xi} \mathcal{P}(\tau, q^*). \end{aligned}$$

Proof: The first equality follows from (5) and the last equality from equation (9). Also, it is clear from the previously described result in [2, Lemma 1, p. 84] that the use of minimum in equation (10) rather than infimum is justified since the distortion measure ρ is convex and lower semicontinuous in y^N and Λ is compact by assumption. The second equality holds because of equation (11) and the theorem follows. *QED.*

Thus, solution of (10) determines a quantizer q^* and least favorable distribution τ^* as well as the corresponding mean quantization error. An analytic solution is generally not available for three reasons: first, Λ is continuous and contains an

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{P}(\tau^*, q^*) \\
&= \sup_{\tau \in \Xi} \min_{q^N \in \Psi} \int_{\theta \in \Lambda} d\theta \cdot \tau(\theta) \cdot \left(\int_{y^M \in Y^N} dy^N \int_{x^M \in X^M} dx^M \cdot f^\theta(x^M, y^N) \cdot \rho(x^M, y^N) \right) \\
&= \sup_{\tau \in \Xi} \min_{q^N \in \Psi} \int_{\theta \in \Lambda} d\theta \cdot \tau(\theta) \cdot \left(\sum_{i=1}^N \int_{x^M \in S_i^M} dx^M \cdot p^\theta(x^M) \cdot \rho(x^M, y_i^N) \right) \\
&= \min_{q^N \in \Psi} \sup_{\theta \in \Lambda} \sum_{i=1}^N \int_{x^M \in S_i^M} dx^M \cdot \left(\rho(x^M, y_i^N) \cdot \int_{\theta \in \Lambda} d\theta \cdot \tau(\theta) \cdot p^\theta(x^M) \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

uncountable number of θ ; secondly, Ξ the class of all *a priori* distributions is uncountable; and thirdly, the quantization problem is non-linear. Thus, the problem, in general, involves solving an uncountable number of integrals and taking the minimum over that set which appears intractable. However, two theorems suggest an approach to solve (10), within any previously given error threshold, when the class of sources Λ is continuous.

Theorem 2: Let Λ be a continuous and compact parameter space with respect to a given a non-negative distortion measure ρ , and let there be given a finite number of quantization levels, N . Then, there exists a finite set $\{\theta_i^* \in \Lambda\}_{i=1}^m$ where $m \leq N$, which determines both a least-favorable distribution τ^* and quantizer q^* for class Λ such that q^* and τ^* are solutions to (10).

Proof: The optimal quantizer given by a partition $\{S_i^*\}_{i=1}^N$ and reproduction space Y^* , minimizes the maximum quantization error over Λ for a given distortion measure ρ in the sense of equations (2) and (3). It is also apparent that the optimal $\{S_i^*\}_{i=1}^N$ and space $Y^* = \{y_i^*\}_{i=1}^N$ also determine a class of discrete sources P with distributions given by:

$$w^\theta(y_i^*) = \int_{x^M \in S_i^*} dx^M \cdot p^\theta(x^M). \tag{12}$$

Thus, P is a class of discrete sources with parameter given by $\theta \in \Lambda$. Let $H(P^\theta)$ denote the average length of the best code for P^θ . Therefore, given any θ_i and θ_j such that $\{\theta_i, \theta_j\} \in \Lambda$, the redundancy between their codes may be defined as:

$$r(P^{\theta_i}, P^{\theta_j}) = |H(P^{\theta_i}) - H(P^{\theta_j})|. \tag{13}$$

The problem becomes one to minimize the maximum redundancy over P by finding a source best matched to the class of sources. However this is a source matching problem which is solved by finding the channel capacity between the parameter space Λ and the output space given by $Y^* = \{y_i^*\}_{i=1}^N$ (Davisson, IEEE Trans. on Info. Theory vol. IT-26, 1980). The solution of this source matching problem also produces an associated least favorable distribution τ^* over Λ . Utilizing a finite set $\{\theta_i \in \Lambda\}_{i=1}^m$ chosen from an uncountable number of sources can now be seen for the problem by applying [3, Corollary 3, p. 96] which states that for a finite output space Y^* there is a distribution τ^* over Λ that assigns a non-zero probability to only a minimal number of sources $\{\theta_i \in \Lambda\}_{i=1}^m$ and τ^* gives rise to the channel capacity between Λ and Y^* . Also, m can be no larger than the size of the output set, i.e. $m \leq N$ according to [3, Corollary 3, p.96].

Observe that there exists a one-to-one correspondence between each P^θ and some p^θ and that P maps onto the class of all $\{p^\theta\}$. By construction, the quantization and source matching problems correspond directly and solution of one implies solution of the other. *QED.*

Theorem 3: Let there be given a quantizer q^* and distribution τ^* which are a solution to equation (10). Also given are distribution p^θ , a non-negative distortion measure ρ which is convex and lower semicontinuous in y^N and a class of sources with parameter space Λ that is compact with respect to ρ . Then, the following equation is true:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{P}(\tau^*(\theta), q^*) &= \rho(q^*, p^\theta), \quad \tau^*(\theta) > 0 \\
&\leq \rho(q^*, p^\theta), \quad \tau^*(\theta) = 0,
\end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

when q^* and τ^* are the solutions to equation (10), and furthermore, such q^* and τ^* also minimize the maximum mean quantization error over Λ in the sense of equations (2) and (3).

Proof: As shown in Theorem 2, the N -level quantizer problem is equivalent to a source matching problem which is solved by finding the channel capacity between the parameter space Λ and the output space given by $Y^* = \{y_i^*\}_{i=1}^N$. Equation (14) is just a form of a specific condition that must be met by any solution to any channel capacity problem. Such a condition is known as an equalizer rule in its application to statistical risk problems [2, pg. 90]. In this instance, equation (14) specifically follows from a theorem by Gallager in [3, Theorem 4.5.1] which gives an equalizer rule about channel capacity. *QED.*

The approach, then, is use Theorem 2 to find a finite set of sources $\{\theta_i \in \Lambda\}_{i=1}^m$. Use this finite set of representative sources to solve equations (10) and (12), thereby, finding the N -level quantizer q^* that minimizes the maximum mean quantization error for Λ . An approximation to the m sources can be found amongst a judiciously chosen set of J sources where $J \geq N \geq m$, using the following algorithm.

Source Partition Algorithm: The algorithm is adapted from [9] to find a finite set $\{\theta_i \in \Lambda\}_{i=1}^J$ for some integer $J \geq N \geq m$. Relative entropy is used as a measure of the similarity between sources in order to group together within subclasses all sources in a class whose entropies are within a previously specified level of discrepancy. Subsequently, a finite set of representative sources can be selected, one from each subclass. Observe from the above discussion that $\{\theta_i \in \Lambda\}_{i=1}^J$ must contain a subset which approximates the minimal set of m representative sources.

For simplicity of discussion, the algorithm will be given assuming that $M=1$ and each parameter $\theta \in \Lambda$ lies on the real line in the closed interval $[a, b]$. That is, the algorithm is described for a scalar quantizer and a one-dimensional parameter space where $m \leq N$ and m is the size of the minimal set of representative sources. Extension of this method to higher order dimensions and vector quantizers is straightforward. It is also assumed that Λ is compact; for if not, the hull may be added for purposes of computation, and it is necessary to select only those sources which lie in Λ for inclusion in the finite set of subclasses.

The Source Partition algorithm groups all sources into J subclasses, where $J \geq N \geq m$, using relative entropy to measure the similarity between any two sources. (Relative entropy is defined

as $H(p; q) \equiv \sum p(x) \cdot \log(p(x) + q(x))$. An approximation may be used when it is not analytically known.) The algorithm produces a finite set of J parameters $\{\theta_j\}_{j=1}^J$, which partitions $[a, b]$ into J subclasses $\{\Theta_j\}_{j=1}^J$ where $\Theta_j = [\theta_{j-1}, \theta_j]$. Individual Θ_j are chosen such that the relative entropy between two sources in a subclass is less than a given error tolerance ϵ_{sp} .

Algorithm SP (Source Partition)

1. Initialization: Set ϵ_{sp} = an assigned error tolerance; $\theta_0 = a$; $J = 0$.
2. Set $J = J + 1$. Find $\theta_j > \theta_{j-1}$ such that $H(\theta_j; \theta_{j-1}) = \epsilon_{sp}$.
3. If $\theta_j \geq b$ and $J \geq m$, output the set $b \cup \{\theta_j\}$; $\gamma = 0, \dots, J - 1$.
4. If $\theta_j < b$, goto 2. If $\theta_j \geq b$ and $J < m$ then $\epsilon = \epsilon/2$ and goto 1.

Clearly, the finite set $\{\theta_j \in \Lambda\}_{j=1}^J$ contains a subset that approximates $\{\theta_i^* \in \Lambda\}_{i=1}^m$ which is the minimal set of m representative sources. Furthermore, by construction, in that subset there must exist some θ_j which is within ϵ_{sp} of θ_i^* for each and every $1 \leq i \leq m$. Therefore, the finite set $\{\theta_j \in \Lambda\}_{j=1}^J$ can be used to find the desired q^* which minimizes the maximum mean quantization error in the sense of (2) and (3). Succinctly:

Algorithm 1

1. Apply Algorithm SP to select a finite set of representative sources $\{\theta_i\}_{i=1}^J$ for given N .
2. Use the finite set of representative sources $\{\theta_i\}_{i=1}^J$ which give the inputs and their distributions, and a scalar (vector) algorithm which is optimal for the given distortion measure $\rho(\cdot)$, (e.g. Lloyd [5], Linde [4]) to find q_N^* and τ_N^* which solve (14) and (10).
3. Output q_N^* , τ_N^* and $\mathcal{P}(\tau_N^*, q_N^*)$ and stop.

The algorithm achieves its optimal performance on a fixed dimension basis unlike universal quantizers which generally require increasing dimensionality to achieve their full theoretical performance capability. The convergence is shown, below.

Theorem 4: Let Λ be a continuous and compact parameter space with respect to a given a non-negative distortion measure ρ . Also, let an error threshold be given by $\epsilon_{sp} = \epsilon \cdot 2^K$ for some non-negative ϵ where $K \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$. Fix ϵ . Furthermore, let q^* and τ^* be the solution to equation (10). Define q_K^N as the N -level quantizer and τ_K^N as the least favorable distribution found by application of Algorithm 1 for a given K and N . Then, the following are true:

Part 1: For fixed N and increasing K the corresponding sequence of quantizers $\{q_K^N\}_{K=1}^\infty$ converges in probability to an optimal N -level quantizer q^* that minimizes the mean quantization error in the sense of equations (2) and (3), and which is also the solution to equation (10).

Part 2: For fixed K and increasing N the corresponding sequence of quantizers which is denoted by $\{q_K^N\}_{N=1}^\infty$ produces a corresponding minimum mean quantization error sequence $\{\mathcal{P}^*(\tau_K^N, q_K^N)\}_{N=1}^\infty$ that converges to zero.

Proof: Part 1 is addressed first. Recall from Theorem 2 that, for fixed N , there exists a set $\{\theta_i^* \in \Lambda\}_{i=1}^m$ which determines q^* . Algorithm SP finds a set $\{\theta_j \in \Lambda\}_{j=1}^J$ where $J \geq N \geq m$, which approximates $\{\theta_i^* \in \Lambda\}_{i=1}^m$ within an error threshold ϵ_{sp} . That is, in $\{\theta_j \in \Lambda\}_{j=1}^J$ there must exist some θ_j which is within ϵ_{sp} of θ_i^* for each and every i . This is true because, by the construction of Algorithm SP, any two sources in a subclass have relative entropy no greater than ϵ_{sp} .

Clearly, for increasing K the size of the set $\{\theta_j \in \Lambda\}_{j=1}^J$

will also increase; that is, J will vary with K for any fixed N . Also, the error threshold $\epsilon_{sp} = \epsilon \cdot 2^K$ varies inversely with increasing K . The set of representative sources $\{\theta_j \in \Lambda\}_{j=1}^J$ will be denoted by $\{\theta_j^K \in \Lambda\}_{j=1}^{J(K)}$ for this proof to explicitly indicate its dependence upon K and a previously-fixed ϵ .

Given K there must exist some θ_j^K which is within ϵ_{sp} of θ_i^* for each and every i ; that is: $H(\theta_j^K; \theta_i^*) \leq (\epsilon \cdot 2^K)$ for some j corresponding to each i . Clearly, for increasing K the error threshold converges: $\{(\epsilon \cdot 2^K) - (\epsilon \cdot 2^{K+1})\}_{K=1}^\infty \rightarrow 0$. Accordingly, for all i there is a corresponding sequence $\{\theta_j^K\}_{K=1}^\infty$ where $\theta_j^K \in \{\theta_j \in \Lambda\}_{j=1}^{J(K)}$. This implies, because $H(\theta_j^K; \theta_i^*) \leq (\epsilon \cdot 2^K)$, that an associated sequence $\{H(\theta_j^K; \theta_i^*) - H(\theta_j^{K+1}; \theta_i^*)\} \rightarrow 0$ as $K \rightarrow \infty$ for all such i , and Part 1 of the theorem follows.

Part 2 is shown by demonstrating a correspondence between the mean quantization error sequence and calculating Sakrison's rate distortion function for a class of sources.

Precisely, using a result from [9], for any class of sources described in this theorem and given a fixed N and K there is an optimal approximation to Sakrison's rate distortion function for that class of sources. Further, this N -level rate distortion function can be found from a finite set $\{\theta_i^{**} \in \Lambda\}_{i=1}^n$, where $N \geq n$. In turn the set depends solely upon a given error threshold $\epsilon \cdot 2^K$ according to a result in [9]. Denote by $R_K^N(D)$ the optimal N -level approximation to Sakrison's rate distortion function. In [9] it was shown that the sequence of N -level approximations $\{R_K^N(D)\}_{N=1}^\infty$ converges to Sakrison's rate distortion function $R^N(D)$ for increasing N and fixed K .

Clearly the finite set $\{\theta_j^K \in \Lambda\}_{j=1}^{J(K)}$ produced by Algorithm SP for the quantization problem contains a subset that can also be used to approximate $\{\theta_i^{**} \in \Lambda\}_{i=1}^n$ for the rate distortion problem, for a given N and K . That is, in $\{\theta_j^K \in \Lambda\}_{j=1}^{J(K)}$ there must exist some θ_j^K which is within ϵ_{sp} of θ_i^{**} for each and every i . This is true because, by construction of Algorithm SP, any two sources in a subclass have relative entropy no greater than ϵ_{sp} . Therefore, the finite set $\{\theta_j^K \in \Lambda\}_{j=1}^{J(K)}$ given by a particular K can also be used to approximate $R_K^N(D)$ using the following approach: perform an exhaustive search over the set of rate distortion functions produced by the associated set $\{\theta_j^K \in \Lambda\}_{j=1}^{J(K)}$; select the largest-valued rate distortion function to approximate $R_K^N(D)$; and denote the approximation as $\tilde{R}_K^N(D)$. A sequence $\{\tilde{R}_K^N(D)\}_{N=1}^\infty$ is produced by fixing K and increasing the value of N .

Apparently, there exists a correspondence between this particular quantization problem considered, herein, and the rate distortion problem in [9]. For fixed K and a given N denote by $\mathcal{P}^*(\tau_K^N, q_K^N)$ the mean quantization error found from application of Algorithm 1 over set $\{\theta_j \in \Lambda\}_{j=1}^J$. Specifically, it is then clear that for fixed K and increasing N the mean quantization error sequence $\{\mathcal{P}^*(\tau_K^N, q_K^N)\}_{N=1}^\infty$ converges to zero if and only if the corresponding sequence of rate distortion functions $\{R_K^N(D)\}_{N=1}^\infty$ converges to Sakrison's rate distortion function, $R^N(D)$.

Convergence of $\{\tilde{R}_K^N(D)\}_{N=1}^\infty$ is now shown. It suffices to show that $\tilde{R}_{K+1}^N(D) \geq \tilde{R}_K^N(D)$ for all K because $R^N(D)$ achieves the supremum for fixed K . Consider the approximation produced by the set of representative sources $\{\theta_j^K \in \Lambda\}_{j=1}^{J(K)}$. Let $\theta_s \in \{\theta_j^K \in \Lambda\}_{j=1}^{J(K)}$ produce the smallest mutual information. Case 1: find a $\theta_g \in \{\theta_j^{K+1} \in \Lambda\}_{j=1}^{J(K+1)}$ that produces the greatest mutual

information, such that $\theta_g \notin \{\theta_j^k \in \Lambda\}_{j=1}^{J(K)}$ and where the mutual information produced by θ_g is greater than or equal to that which is produced by θ_s . Thus, (15) must be satisfied and holds true:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{R}_K^N(D) &= \sup_{\tau_K^N \in \mathcal{E}^N} \inf_{Q \in Q(D)} \int_{\theta \in \Lambda} I(p^\theta; Q) \cdot \tau_K^N(\theta) d\theta \\ &= \max_{\tau_K^N \in \mathcal{E}^N} \min_{Q \in Q(D)} \sum_{\theta \in \Lambda} I(p^\theta; Q) \cdot \tau_K^N(\theta) \\ &\leq \max_{\tau_K^N \in \mathcal{E}^N} \min_{Q \in Q(D)} \sum_{\theta \in \Lambda} \tau_K^N(\theta) I(p^\theta; Q) + \tau_K^N(\theta_s) I(p^{\theta_s}; Q) \\ &\leq \max_{\tau_K^{N+1} \in \mathcal{E}^{N+1}} \min_{Q \in Q(D)} \sum_{\theta \in \Lambda} \tau_K^{N+1}(\theta) \cdot I(p^\theta; Q) \\ &= \bar{R}_K^{N+1}(D). \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

The third equality in equation (15) occurs because the N representative sources form a finite class. The first inequality is true because the mutual information produced by θ_g is greater than that of θ_s . The second inequality is a result of [8].

Case 2: There does not exist a $\theta_g \in \{\theta_j^{K+1} \in \Lambda\}_{j=1}^{J(K+1)}$ that produces the greatest mutual information, such that $\theta_g \notin \{\theta_j^k \in \Lambda\}_{j=1}^{J(K)}$ and where the mutual information produced by θ_g is greater than or equal to that produced by θ_s . Clearly, $\bar{R}_K^N(D) = \bar{R}_{K+1}^N(D)$. In both cases, the sequence $\{\bar{R}_K^N(D)\}_{N=1}^\infty$ is non-decreasing and bounded since $R^N(D)$ achieves the supremum for fixed K . Part 2 is verified and the theorem follows. QED.

A statistical decision technique by Nelson [6] suggests another way to find the least-favorable distribution τ^* and the optimal quantizer q^* which minimizes the maximum mean quantization error. The following summarizes the technique:

Algorithm 2

1. Choose an arbitrary distribution τ_0^* over $\{\theta_i\}_{i=0}^{J-1}$ and calculate $\mathcal{P}_0(\tau_0^*, q^*)$ using an algorithm (e.g. Lloyd etc.) which is optimal for a distortion measure ρ . Select an error threshold ε . Let $k=k+1$.
2. k th iteration: If $\varepsilon \leq \max_{\theta \in \Lambda} \rho_k(q_k^*, p^\theta) - \mathcal{P}_k(\tau_k^*, q_k^*)$ then output $\tau_k^*, q_k^*, \mathcal{P}_k(\tau_k^*, q_k^*)$ and stop.
3. Else, construct a new distribution τ_{k+1}^* over $\{\theta_i\}_{i=0}^{J-1}$ as follows:
 - (a). Let m equal the number of θ such that $\rho_k(q_k^*, p^\theta) \neq 0$.
 - (b). Define a class of distributions γ such that $\gamma(i) = \lambda(i)/m + (1-\lambda(i)) \cdot \tau_k^*(\theta_i)$ where $0 < \lambda(i) \leq 1$.
 - (c). $\tau_{k+1}^*(\theta_i) = \lambda^*(i)/m + (1-\lambda^*(i)) \cdot \tau_k^*(\theta_i)$ where $\lambda^*(i) = \arg \max_\lambda \mathcal{P}_k(\gamma(i), q^*)$. Go to 2.

Theorem 5: Let Λ be a continuous and compact parameter space with respect to a given a non-negative distortion measure ρ . Let an error threshold be given by $\varepsilon_{sp} = \varepsilon \div 2^K$ for some non-negative ε where $K \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$. Fix ε and let q^* and τ^* be a solution to equation (10). Define q_K^N as the N -level quantizer and τ_K^N as the least favorable distribution found by application of Algorithm 2 for a given K and N . Then:

Part 1: For fixed N and increasing K the corresponding sequence of quantizers $\{q_K^N\}_{K=1}^\infty$ converges in probability to an optimal N -level quantizer q^* that minimizes the mean quantization error in the sense of equations (2) and (3), and which is also the solution to equation (10).

Part 2: For fixed K and increasing N the corresponding sequence of quantizers which is denoted by $\{q_K^N\}_{N=1}^\infty$ produces a corresponding minimum mean quantization error

sequence $\{\mathcal{P}^*(\tau_K^N, q_K^N)\}_{N=1}^\infty$ that converges to zero.

Proof: It follows the one given for Theorem 4. QED.

IV. AN EXAMPLE

Algorithm 1 is used for the M -dimensional class of independent and identically distributed $N(\mu, \sigma^2)$ Gaussian sources with parameter $\sigma^2 \in [0.25, 1.25] \cup [2.25, 2.5] \equiv \Lambda$ and where $\mu = 0$. ρ is the squared error distortion measure, and $\varepsilon = 0.05$. The figure shows the results when K is a held fixed and N allowed to increase, and where $\varepsilon_{sp} = \varepsilon \div 2^K$.

Figure 1

V. CONCLUSIONS

When it is known that a source belongs to a class of parameterized sources, an approach presented in this paper may be used to find the quantizer which minimizes the maximum mean quantization error. The approach interprets the problem in terms of statistical risk, and uses relative entropy to measure distortion. Two algorithms were presented and shown to be convergent. An example demonstrated the result.

VI. REFERENCES

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